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DENTISTRY 2023 NOVI SAD**

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On behalf of the Organizing and Scientific Committee, we are pleased to welcome you all at the International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2023 Novi Sad.

The Scientific and Organization Committee made an effort to make a conference that has scientific value and is also interesting for dental professionals, although it is held in hybrid form.

You will meet an exceptional program covering different topics, from basic research areas to areas within daily practice of Restorative Dentistry, Endodontics, Prosthodontics, Oral Surgery and Implantology, Periodontology, Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry.

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APPLICATION OF SPHERICAL TiO₂ NANOPARTICLES AS MODIFICATION OF GLASS-IONOMER CEMENTS

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Abstract:

Introduction: Because of the greater surface-to-volume ratio and antibacterial properties of nanoparticles (NP), they have found applications in restorative dentistry. Among the various existing nanomaterials, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) has been the subject of numerous studies as an inorganic additive due to its chemical stability, biocompatibility, and potential improvement in the mechanical properties of dental restorative materials.

Aim: To microscopically assess whether the TiO₂ forms clusters and agglomerates when incorporated into the ionomer matrix.

Methods and Materials: Two commercially available GIC materials - Fuji IX (Fuji IX GP, GC International, Japan) and Ketac Molar (Ketac Molar EasyMix™- 3 M/ESPE, Maple-wood, Minnesota, USA) were incorporated with TiO₂ powder at 5% in the form of spheres NP with an average size of 20 nm. The flexural strength of both modified GIC materials was tested and the obtained fracture surface was analyzed using SEM.

Results: The microscopic images of both tested TiO₂ modified GICs showed the formation of microscopic clusters of these NPs on the tested surface without microscopically visible signs of their uniform incorporation into the ionomer matrix.

Conclusion: When TiO₂ nanoparticles are dispersed in a liquid, they are showing a high surface energy, which can be reduced by the formation of clusters. Understanding the factors that drive nanoparticle clustering is important for developing effective strategies to control their aggregation, which is critical for many nanotechnology applications. This study confirmed that spherical TiO₂-NPs are not recommended as a potential modifier of GIC materials because their uniform distribution throughout the mixed material is very difficult to achieve.